

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF THE NATURE OF FAILURES OCCURRING IN EQUIPMENT AND TECHNICAL MEANS USED IN OIL AND GAS WELLS

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Abstract

Most of the oil and gas fields of the Republic of Azerbaijan are experiencing their last operational life [1]. Although the vast majority of oil fields in the country are located on the Absheron Peninsula and in Gobustan, large volumes of oil and gas are extracted from offshore fields [2]. Of the 81 identified oil and gas fields, 54 are on land, and 27 are in the Caspian Sea area belonging to Azerbaijan [3]. The full process of exploitation of these deposits is currently carried out only at 59 of them.

Currently, the total number of wells on SOCAR's balance sheet is more than 6,500 units, of which about 95% are included in the current fund. The remaining wells are inactive due to conservation and liquidation [5].

The article is devoted to the analysis of the nature of failures occurring in equipment and technical means used in oil and gas wells.

Keywords: Oil well, cause of failures, equipment resource.

Introduction. When drilling wells, as well as during their operation, various complications may occur (absorption of drilling mud, occurrence of oil and gas and water manifestations, violation of the stability of the well wall, jamming of tools and equipment in the well due to breakdowns and jams, etc.) occur [7]. As a result of mining experiments, it was found that the implementation of applications related to the prevention of complications arising in wells, the technological processes spent on their subsequent liquidation are technically simple and economically advantageous. Thus, each emerging complication, being a serious cause of other complications, makes it difficult to eliminate them, creates the basis for large expenditures of material and technical means, time, energy and labor [8]. Therefore, of particular importance is the development of preventive measures for the early detection of failures and accidents that may occur during the drilling of wells, their prevention, as well as the elimination of the possibility of occurrence for other reasons.

On the other hand, accidents of various nature occur in the oil sector (equipment breakdowns for various reasons, deformations and ruptures, formation of sand, salt, paraffin plugs, etc.) and failures [9]. Accidents during drilling and operation occur mainly due to the violation of the integrity of the borehole column, wear

of the thickness of their walls due to corrosion corrosion, deformations of various nature, as well as other deviations, failure of the well engine, deformation of the drill bit, they are also associated with objects that got into the well during work and fastening.

Instruments and technical means used in geophysical methods of assessing the technical condition of the well, starting with the drilling process, at later stages of the well operation process, can lead to maintaining the well in working condition for various reasons (breakage of logging cable, wire, falling into the wellbore due to faults and jams of various nature in the lowered into the well with instruments and instruments, etc.).

As a result of our research, it was found that the most intense failures occur in such equipment as deep-rod and electric submersible pumps, gas lift valves, packers, anchors, etc.). At the same time, the main causes of accidents are the processes of corrosion corrosion, the formation of salt deposits and the occurrence of deformations of various nature [10].

Figure 1 shows the failures and their numbers that occur in some downhole equipment (rod deep and electric submersible pumps, gas lift installations).

Our research has shown that the average service life of deep water pumps is 30-48 days, while for electric submersible pumps this period is 60-140 days, and for gas lift valves-120-150 days.

Figure 1 Failures occurring in downhole equipment and their number.

Thus, taking into account the above, it can be concluded that the expected failure in the corresponding wells and, consequently, the intensity of the repair and restoration work carried out during the year is 3-6 times.

The analysis of the causes of accidents in the oil and gas production departments (NGDU) of the Republic of Azerbaijan, occurring during drilling or operation, shows that they, being at different depths, in different conditions, are generally classified into two groups: geological and technical. In all cases, the identification and elimination of these shortcomings requires the development of special technical and technological approaches, while the appropriate control method and the correct choice of tools and equipment in the well to eliminate the causes of the accident (individual approach) becomes more relevant. And the solution of the issue, in turn, highlights the need to obtain complete and detailed information about the situation inside the well. The fund of wells in need of repair is changing with increasing dynamics. So, over the past decade, this indicator for SOCAR has increased 1.6 times. If in 2013 the number of wells of this type was up to 800, then by the end of 2021 this figure approached 1,250.

Apparently, this figure is quite large, and the implementation of technological measures aimed at giving wells of this type a "second life", in turn, requires the creation of new tools and equipment, increasing their leading characteristics, reducing durability.

In this regard, the study of the nature of accidents at oil and gas wells, their extensive analysis and improvement of methods of their elimination, as well as instrumental, hardware and hardware base with the use of innovative technologies are becoming more relevant.

Currently, large-scale repair and restoration work is underway at the wells. These studies were grouped into 12 areas collectively and in 66 different sections [13]. In addition, maintenance of various levels is carried out in the wells during each year. These works include replacement of pumps in production wells, repair of broken pipes and rods, cleaning of the well column from paraffin, salts and other deposits, etc.

Conclusions. Thus, taking into account the above, accidents at production wells and the complications caused by them can be dried as follows:

- accidents caused by prolonged operation of the front side of pipes and rods used in the well;
- accidents caused by the failure of engines, installations, devices, packers and elements located in the lower part of the well pipeline;
- accidents with breakage of logging cable and overhead wire;
- accidents during the restoration of wells that have ceased their activities as a result of complications of accidents that have occurred;
- accidents related to the use of non-standard equipment inside the well and as a result of breakage and falling of foreign objects - bolts, nuts, dies, parts of tested keys when working in the wellhead.

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